

Microbiological Characteristics of Necrotizing Fasciitis at Sultan Qaboos University Hospital, Muscat, Oman: A Retrospective Study

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Introduction

Necrotizing fasciitis is a rapidly progressive, life-threatening infection involving the fascia and subcutaneous tissues. It is commonly associated with underlying conditions such as diabetes mellitus and immunosuppression. The lower limbs are the most frequently affected site. Microbiologically, it is classified into type I (polymicrobial) and type II (monomicrobial) infections. Early recognition, prompt surgical debridement, and timely empirical antimicrobial therapy remain essential to reduce morbidity and mortality.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective study was conducted between 2015 and 2021, including operatively confirmed necrotizing fasciitis and available clinical data, with at least 12 months of follow-up. Data collected included comorbidities, site of infection, and management strategies (surgical and medical). Microbiological profiles and antimicrobial resistance patterns were analyzed, with assessment of their association with 30-day mortality.

Results

A total of 43 patients were included, with a male predominance (72%) and a median age of 61 years (range 18–85). Diabetes mellitus was present in 72% of cases. The lower limbs were the most commonly affected site (72%). Type I and type II infections were nearly equally distributed (51% vs 49%). The most frequently isolated organisms were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* (each 9%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, MRSA, and *Proteus mirabilis* (each 7%). Extended organisms were identified in 5%. Multidrug-resistant (MDR) organisms were present in 19% of cases, most commonly MDR *Pseudomonas*. The 30-day mortality rate was 7%.

Conclusion

Necrotizing fasciitis predominantly affected males, with diabetes as the main risk factor and lower limbs as the commonest site. Both polymicrobial and monomicrobial infections were equally observed. Gram-negative and MDR organisms were relatively frequent; however, MDR infection was not associated with increased mortality. Early diagnosis, aggressive surgical management, and appropriate antimicrobial therapy likely contributed to the low mortality rate. These findings highlight the importance of understanding local microbiological and resistance patterns.

Keywords

antibiotics, microbiology, mortality, multidrug resistance, necrotizing fasciitis